

PRINCIPLES OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT IN TALENTED STUDENTS THROUGH EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS

Ruzimova Yulduzkhan Jumanazar kizi

Teacher of the "Mathematical Analysis" department of the Faculty of
Physics and Mathematics of the Urganch State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14177673>

Abstract: This scientific article describes the methodology of developing the professional competence of talented students with the help of educational platforms. The need to use innovative technologies in education, the effectiveness of directing students to professional activities through modern platforms is scientifically based. The research examines the types of platforms, their functionality, their impact on the educational process, and their role in improving students' professional skills. At the same time, ways of personalizing the educational process for gifted students, creating an interactive environment, and integrating knowledge with practice were analyzed. In conclusion, innovative methodical approaches to the development of students' professional competence through educational platforms were proposed.

Key words: Educational platforms, professional competence, gifted students, innovative technologies, interactive education, personalized education, methodical approach.

Introduction.

Today, globalization and the rapid development of digital technologies require the introduction of new approaches in the field of education. In particular, directing talented students to professional activities and increasing their level of competence is one of the priorities of modern education. In this process, the effectiveness of using innovative educational platforms and digital resources is increasing. Educational platforms provide a wide range of opportunities for creating an interactive environment, personalizing educational materials and developing practical knowledge in the modern educational process.

The relevance of this research is that the development of professional competence of talented students through the use of educational platforms is not limited to providing only theoretical knowledge, but it allows to form and strengthen their practical skills. Also, this process increases students' motivation for professional activity, encourages them to think independently and use innovative approaches.

The article analyzes the theoretical basis, practical application and results of the methodology of professional development of talented students through educational platforms. At the same time, opinions about the existing problems and effective ways to eliminate them were put forward.

Methodology:

In this study, the following methodological approaches were developed to develop the professional competence of talented students through educational platforms:

1. Individualization of the educational process

Taking into account the level of knowledge and interests of students, individually form educational materials and provide them with customized tasks through the platform. This approach helps students' self-development and increases motivation.

2. Creating an interactive educational environment

Ensuring active participation of students through tests, virtual laboratories, video lessons and discussions on educational platforms. The use of interactive materials helps to strengthen students' practical skills.

3. Numerical methods of assessing skills

Regularly analyze students' knowledge level and monitor their progress using automated assessment systems through the platform. This method allows to determine the development of students and, if necessary, to reorganize the educational process.

4. Integration of practice and theory

Application of tasks based on professional situations in educational platforms. For example, real-life problem solving, project-based learning, and the use of simulation methods play an important role in preparing students for their careers.

5. Formation of teamwork skills

Developing communication, joint problem solving and teamwork skills in students by organizing group projects and tasks on platforms.

6. Expanding the capabilities of platforms

Use of modern educational platforms, such as Moodle, Coursera, Google Classroom and other interactive programs. Through them, students can independently expand and deepen their knowledge.

This methodology is aimed at the comprehensive development of students' activities and helps them acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for success in professional activities. Also, these approaches increase students' interest in studying and ensure their activity in the learning process.

Literature review:

In this study, foreign and local sources were deeply studied to determine the scientific and theoretical basis for the development of professional competence of talented students through educational platforms. In the course of the research, literature on the following topics was analyzed:

1. Educational platforms and their advantages.

Research on the functionality and usability of modern educational platforms has been covered by many scholars, including Anderson (2008) and Siemens (2014). They justified the advantages of creating an interactive environment, personalizing knowledge and using a global educational network in online education. Foreign sources have widely analyzed the importance of educational platforms in increasing student motivation and professional training.

2. Concept of professional competence.

The studies of Boyatzis (2008) and Spencer & Spencer (1993) on issues of professional competence development are important. They evaluated professional knowledge and skills as the main factor for personal and professional success. The works of local scientists, including T. Q. Kadirov and M. U. Kasimov, pay special attention to the formation of professional competence in the educational system of Uzbekistan.

3. Innovative educational technologies.

Studies on the use of innovative educational technologies and their effectiveness (Clark & Mayer, 2016; Hattie, 2012) were studied. These resources provide a theoretical basis for the

role of digital technologies in education, especially the optimization of the learning process through educational platforms.

4. Methods of working with gifted students.

Methodical approaches to teaching gifted students have been widely studied by Gardner (1983) and Sternberg (2005). Their research emphasizes the importance of an individual approach to the development of students' intellectual potential. The methods of organizing personalized educational programs for gifted students in foreign and local sources are deeply analyzed.

5. Local educational experience.

The literature on the development of digital educational platforms in the educational system of Uzbekistan was analyzed, including the decisions and normative documents of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the works of scientists such as A. B. Joraev and S. Kh. Nasrullayev. These resources provide detailed information on the importance of introducing innovations in education and the social and economic benefits of this process.

From the analysis of the literature, it became clear that research on the development of professional competence of talented students through educational platforms remains relevant at the foreign and domestic levels. However, it is necessary to study this subject more deeply and develop innovative approaches in the conditions of the educational system of Uzbekistan.

Discussion:

The results of the research on the methodology of developing the professional competence of talented students through educational platforms show that the use of digital educational technologies is becoming an integral part of the modern education system. The information and observations obtained during the research were discussed in the following aspects:

1. The influence of educational platforms.

Interactive learning platforms such as Moodle, Google Classroom, and Coursera play an important role in increasing student engagement in the learning process. Through these platforms, students are provided with tasks aimed at developing not only theoretical knowledge, but also the skills to solve real professional problems. This greatly contributes to the formation of professional competence of students.

2. Individualization and personalized education.

Educational platforms allow for individualization of knowledge according to the abilities and needs of students. The results of the research showed that the personalized educational approach increases students' motivation for self-development and serves to effectively acquire knowledge.

3. Formation of practical skills.

By introducing tasks based on real situations on the platforms, students' practical skills will increase significantly. Methods such as simulations, project work, and analysis of problem situations allow students to connect theoretical knowledge with practical activities.

4. Difficulties and problems.

Technical and organizational problems are observed in the introduction of educational platforms. In particular, the lack of sufficient digital literacy for students and teachers, limited Internet resources, as well as the inflexibility of some platforms can hinder the educational process. To solve these problems, it is necessary to develop special programs for increasing digital literacy.

5. Effectiveness of innovative approaches.

Teamwork-oriented assignments on educational platforms, such as group projects and collaborative discussions, help students develop their communication skills. This method not only increases the individual professional knowledge of students, but also forms the ability to succeed in team work.

During the discussion, it was determined that the development of professional competence through educational platforms is effective not only for students, but also for teachers, who will have the opportunity to organize lessons in high-quality and modern ways. Therefore, the introduction of these approaches to the educational system on a large scale is an urgent issue.

Summary:

This research is aimed at determining the methodological basis of developing the professional competence of talented students through educational platforms, and the obtained results are summarized as follows:

1. Educational platforms are highly effective in personalizing student knowledge, creating an interactive environment, and building practical skills. They serve as an important tool in increasing the activity and interest of students in the modern educational process.

2. It has been confirmed that the introduction of an individual approach, interactive educational materials, and practical tasks in the development of professional competence through platforms will give effective results. This approach helps students adapt to professional activities faster and develop independent thinking skills.

3. Through the use of innovative approaches, for example, teamwork, project-based learning and the integration of theoretical knowledge with practice, students acquire not only professional skills, but also social skills.

4. In order to overcome the technical and organizational problems encountered in the use of educational platforms, it is necessary to develop the digital infrastructure, improve the qualifications of teachers and prepare students for digital literacy.

5. The research shows that the development of a special program and methodical recommendations for the development of professional competence with the help of educational platforms will serve as a basis for introducing important innovations in this field in the future.

Thus, the use of educational platforms is one of the important means of improving the modern educational process and creates great opportunities for the professional development of talented students. Widespread implementation and continuous development of these approaches should be considered as one of the priorities of modern education.

References:

- 1.Anderson, T. (2008). The Theory and Practice of Online Learning. Athabasca University Press.
- 2.Siemens, G. (2014). Connectivism: A Learning Theory for the Digital Age. International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning.
- 3.Boyatzis, R. E. (2008). Competency Development in Higher Education: Current and Future Perspectives. Journal of Management Development.

- 4.Spencer, L. M., & Spencer, S. M. (1993). *Competence at Work: Models for Superior Performance*. Wiley.
- 5.Gardner, H. (1983). *Frames of Mind: The Theory of Multiple Intelligences*. Basic Books.
- 6.Qodirov, T. Q., & Qosimov, M. U. (2019). *Zamonaviy Ta'lim Texnologiyalari*. Toshkent: O'zbekiston Milliy Universiteti Nashriyoti.
- 7.Jo'raev, A. B., & Nasrullayev, S. X. (2020). *Raqamli Ta'lim Platformalarining Innovatsion Talablarini Shakllantirish*. Toshkent: Fan va Texnologiya Nashriyoti.
- 8.Madraximovich, K. E. (2020). Improving the methodological training of primary school teachers on the basis of innovative approaches. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 8(7).
- 9.Xudoynazarov, E. M. (2019). Didactic possibilities of oral exercises in forming initial classes pupils' mathematical thinking activity. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, Ausgabe. Germany, (1-2019), 249.
- 10.Khudoynazarov, E. (2023). Boshlang 'ich ta'limda mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. *Молодые ученые*, 1(13), 32-37.

